

Performance Evaluation of Nepal Life and LIC A Comparative Analysis of Earnings and Profitability Indicators

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to compare the financial performance between the two largest private sector domestic and joint venture life insurers in Nepal. The study concludes that in FY 2012/13, both Nepal Life and LICs has significantly grown their revenue, assets, net profit, life fund and their contribution in life insurance industry is remarkable. The performance of Nepal Life is relatively better than LIC but in some perspective, LIC did perform better. Among 8 private sector life insurers, sample is selected on the basis of highest assets owned by insurers from each category. The whole analysis is based on secondary data. Data are analysed on CAMELS parameter confine on earnings and profitability ratios.

KEY WORDS: Life Insurance, Financial Performance, CAMELS Parameter

BACKGROUND

The insurance industry plays a critical role, providing individuals and businesses with a broad spectrum of financial security products and playing a major role in financial intermediation, thus enhancing a nation's financial and economic development. Individuals and their families look to insurance companies to provide life insurance, retirement income, health insurance, and automobile and homeowners property and liability coverage (Baltensperger, 2011). The insurance in developed countries has become a part of life but in developing countries like Nepal, the industry is gradually developed.

Insurance industry in Nepal is not well recognised as banking industries. There are limited studies have carried out in insurance sector whereas banking sector has get abundant attention by researchers

and academicians. If we go back to the history, both bank and insurance companies were evolved in the same decade. First bank was established in 1937 (Nepal Bank Ltd.) and first non life insurance company was established by the same bank in 1947. First life insurance company, *Rastriya Beema Sansthan* was established in 1968 as government undertaking and had started life insurance business in 1972. Organised life insurance industry has already completed 40 years of historical journey (IB, 2012).

Before 1972, Indian life insurance corporations through the agents had collected life insurance premium near about Rs. 40 million per year in informal way which equivalent almost Rs. 600 million total sum assured (World Bank, 2002). Most of the policies of Nepalese nationals were

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returned by LIC India to RBS during 1974/75 after taking consent of the policyholders. During 1972-1988, RBS was single life insurance provider in the country so that customers had no alternatives either on insurance products or on insurance companies.

In 1988, National Life Insurance Company was established in private sector and after 2001, other 7 life companies established. Till date, number of life insurance companies reached to 9¹ and non life reached to 16 (Insurance Board, 2012). Now, customers have opportunity to select best insurers and suitable insurance products as per their requirement.

Customers are becoming aware on service quality of insurers; regulating authority is imposing stringent rules to protect the interest customers. Financial sector is becoming more competitive and the WTO opens the domestic market to multinational companies (CEDA, 2008). In this critical scenario, Nepalese domestic and joint venture insurers require to develop their internal capacity, management capabilities and financial strengths so that they can provide quality service to customers in possible minimum price and able to earn return for shareholders.

Profit is the major concern for any economic organisation on which basis firm can economically sustain and investors get reward against their investment. Insurance companies are not exception. However, profit is uncertain; it rewards to owners instead of taking risk, and provides additional bonus to policyholders against the sacrificing cash for future. Management wants to maximise the value of the firm so premium is fixed accordingly. Profitability is influenced by various factors like size, leverage, growth, volume of capital and liquidity position of the firm (Ayele, 2012).

Life insurance companies perform two major roles in economy. First, they provide financial protection to individual and institution and second, they do the role of financial intermediaries. Universally, life

insurance companies are accepted as the engine of the economic development, good vehicle of saving and investments, remedies of worry and fear and friend of government for social security program. Discussion on importance of life insurance is not scope of this paper, we do focus the study on profitability position of the insurers.

Among 9 players in life insurance industries, ten insurers are taken for the study. The methodology of selection is discussed on section three. General overview of both companies is discussed in the same section.

Brief Overview of Two Companies

Nepal Life Insurance Company: The company was established as domestic private sector life insurer and get license from Insurance Board 2001/04/05 and operated its business in the same year. The company is first private domestic life insurer where 80% capital has contributed by domestic promoters and rest of 20% capital was raised through public offering. The company's total paid up capital at mid July 2013 was Rs. 3 billion.

Life Insurance Corporation (Nepal) Ltd: LIC (Nepal) was established in 2001/08/07 as a joint venture life insurer. The company get 55% capital from LIC (India), 25% capital from Vishal Group Nepal, and rest of 20% raised from general public through public offering. It started operations since September 2001. The majority shareholder LIC (Nepal) is LIC India which was established in 1st September 1956 as a sole undertaking of Government of India. LIC (Nepal) is second joint venture insurance company in the country. The company's total paid up capital at mid July 2013 was Rs. 250 million.

As per direction of Insurance Board, both companies already planned to increase their capital more than Rs. 500 million during FY 2013/14 distributing the bonus share and issuing of rights share. Nepal Life

1 Out of 9, 1 is life and non life insurer (Rastriya Beema Santhan) and Insurance Pool is not counted as insurance company since its nature is like reinsurer. Similarly Deposit Guarantee and Credit Corporation also do insurance of deposit and credit but not recognized as Insurance Company.

performed. The objective of this paper is to compare the financial performance under the earnings and profitability which is a part of the CAMELS parameter (Das, Davies and Podpiera, 2003) of domestic and joint venture life insurance companies. Two largest insurers : Nepal Life, which represent the domestic private insurer and Life Insurance Corporation, which represent the joint venture (Indian investment) insurer have been selected for this study.

There are many similarities between the two companies so that the comparative study has meanings. However, difference also exists between two players in many respects. Some non financial indicators are presented in table 1 in brief. Nepal Life has more staffs, more branches office, more policies, more Board of Directors than LICs. Similarly, LICs has more number of products, more agents. Bonus rate of Nepal Life ranges from Rs. 60 to Rs 80 as per policy and the same is ranges from Rs. 52 to Rs. 70 of LIC. The overview helps the reader two know basic background of the two companies. It can be assumed that LIC has emphasised on cost reduction strategy whereas Nepal Life has focused on larger market with large workforce.

Table 1: Non Financial Indicators of LICs

Indicators	Nepal Life Insurance Company	Life Insurance Corporation (Nepal)
Products types	1. Endowment Policy 2. Money Pay Back 3. Jeevan Sahara 4. Jeeva Saathi 5. Term	1. Endowment Policy 2. Anticipated Endowment 3. Modified Endowment 4. Endowment Single Premium 5. Whole life 6. Term Insurance 7. Special Term
No. Of Members in Board	Promoters – 5 Public- 1 Independent -1 Total - 7	Promoters – 3 Public- 1 Independent -1 Total - 5
Departments	6	6
No of Policies	5,97,882	3,44,553
No. of Staffs	217	97
No. of Branches	23	15
No. of Agents	16,043	25,142
Bonus rate	Rs. 60 – 80 per thousand	Rs. 52 – 70 per thousand

Source: Annual Reports

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Financial performance and efficiency of insurance companies are measured by various methods such as Stochastic Data Envelop Analysis methods (Demerdash, Khodary and Tharwat,2013), Balanced Scorecard and ANP model (Kaplan and Norton, 1996), Stochastic Frontier Analysis approach, (Nawi, Ahmad and Aleng, 2012), CAMELS parameters (Das, Davies and Podpiera, 2005 and Sinha, 2013), Frontier Efficiency Methods (Cummins and Weiss,1998). There are two main approaches in efficient frontier analysis: the econometric approach and the mathematical programming approach (Barros *et al.*, 2005). We, in this article have used CAMEL parameter to measure the efficiency of insurance.

CAMELS parameter was first proposed by Das, Davies and Podpiera to assess the financial health and soundness as well as to evaluate the financial performance of insurance companies. The parameter were first used by International Monetary Fund and The World Bank in first time. The extended form of CAMELS is Capital Adequacy, Assets quality, Reinsurance and Actuarial Issues, Management Soundness, Earnings and Profitability, Liquidity and Sensitivity with Market Risk (The World Bank, 2003). Earnings and Profitability is a component under which Return on Assets, Return on Equity, return on investment assets, operating expenses ratios are calculated and observed the efficiency of the insurers.

Barros, Barroso, and Borges (2005) observe the data of Portuguese insurance companies between 1995 to 2001 using DEA model and they conclude that insurance companies exhibit improvements in

technical efficiency but the deterioration observed in terms of technological change indicates that they are not using puts in accordance with their market price. Some companies have grown productivity during the research period but others decreased.

Biiker, J. A. and Lauvensteijn, M.V. (2008) find from their study undertaken on Dutch life insurance industry that competition by analyzing several factors which may affect the competitive nature of a market and various indirect measurement approaches. They apply the Boone indicator to measure the effects of competition in comparison to other sectors in the Netherlands.

Eling and Luhnen (2009) in their study find that a steady efficiency growth in international insurance markets during the sample period (2002–2006), with large efficiency differences between the 37 countries. The highest efficiency is found for Japan; the lowest for the Philippines. It is further found that the evidence for the expense preference hypothesis (i.e., stock companies are more efficient than mutual and for economies of scale (i.e., larger companies are more efficient than smaller companies). There is only a minor difference between distribution types (agency-based vs. direct writers) and very little evidence for economies of scope (i.e., multi-line insurers are not necessarily more efficient than mono-line insurers). There is not much difference between the two frontier efficiency methodologies data envelopment analysis and stochastic frontier analysis.

Tanveer Ahmad Darzi (2011) in his PhD dissertation entitled "Financial performance of insurance industry in post liberalization era in India" intensively discusses on financial performance of insurance industry on the basis of CAMEL tool. He finds mixed results among the non-life insurance industries.

Norma and Haji (2011) analyze the performance of the insurance companies in Malaysia and Brunei. This study measures the efficiency of life insurance companies in Brunei and Malaysia for the year 2000–2005 by using the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). In the DEA technique,

efficiency is measured by the Malmquist index. The Malmquist efficiency measures are decomposed into two components: efficiency change and technical change index. Efficiency change is again decomposed into pure efficiency and scale efficiency. This finding indicates that the bigger the size of the companies, the higher the probability for the companies to be more efficient in utilizing their inputs to generate more outputs. Due to the positive impact of both efficiency and technical changes, the overall total productivity change for these firms within the period of study is maintained at a value higher than 1.

Akotey, Sackey, Lordina and Amoah (2013) find in Ghana under the study of financial statements of 10 life insurance companies covering a period of eleven years (2000 to 2010) and analyzed through panel regression and observe that gross written premiums have a positive relationship with insurers sales profitability, its relationship with investment income is a negative one. The results showed that life insurers have been incurring large underwriting losses due to overtrading and price undercutting. The results further revealed a setting-off rather than a complementary relationship between underwriting profit and investment income toward the enhancement of the overall profitability of life insurers.

Sinha (2013) compares the financial soundness of two life insurers Bajaj Allianz and ICICI Prudential using CAMELS parameter taking data from 2004/05 to 2009/10. He concludes that both of the companies give mixed results. Several areas have been identified for the improvement of both insurers such as capital adequacy, liquidity, operating expenses.

METHODOLOGY

The objective of this study is to find out whether foreign investment performs better than domestic investment. Further, the paper aims to understand the comparative position of two giant private sector life insurance companies: Nepal Life (domestic) and Life Insurance Corporation (joint venture).

Among 9 life insurers working in Nepal, government owned Rastriya Beena Sansathan is excluded from the sampling frame. Rest of the population is divided into two clusters in first stage. Under domestic category there are 5 life insurers (Nepal, Asian, Surya, Gurans and Prime) and under joint venture or foreign establishment category, there are 3 insurers (National, MetAlico, Life Insurance Corporation (Nepal)). In second stage, largest insurers (on the basis of total assets) from each category was selected. The sample are Nepal Life Insurance (now, Nepal) from domestic and Life Insurance Corporation (now, LIC) from joint venture companies are selected for this study.

The study depends on secondary data sources especially the financial statements and annual reports, brochures and information bulletin published by two firms. Most of the information was obtained through official websites of companies and Insurance Board. Quantitative data are used extensively. Before preparing this paper, sufficient literature were reviewed.

Financial performance of two insurers has compared using six ratios under CAMELS parameter of Earnings and Profitability. The ratios under this parameter are: Investment Income to Investment Assets Ratio, Operating Expenses to Net Premiums Ratio, Management Expenses to Net premiums ratio, Return on Assets, Return on Equity, Net Profit Margin ratio. Besides, different financial indicators of two financial years viz. Assets, equity, life fund, equity, reserves and surplus, life fund and non financial indicators viz. Staffs, agents, no. of branches and life policies etc of latest fiscal year of two insurers also be compared.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Both companies (Nepal Life and LIC) had achieved significant growth in premium income, other income, investment assets, total assets and life fund during the FY 2011/12 and 2012/13. Comparing various financial indicators for FY 2012/13 of Nepal

Life with LIC. Nepal Life stood first, except in amount of reserves and surplus fund and corporate tax paid to government. Growth is another important aspect of the firm which shows direction and rate of change of companies' performance. Table 2 depicts major financial indicators of two companies and their growth rate between FY 2011/12 and 2012/13

Table 2: Financial Indicators of Nepal Life and LIC

Amount in NRs. Million

FINANCIAL INDICATORS	Nepal Life			LIC		
	2011/12	2012/13	Change	2011/12	2012/13	Change
Total Assets	8,096.41	10,517.25	30%	6,901.47	9,314.92	35%
Total Capital	375.00	375.00	0%	250.00	250.00	0%
Reserves and Surplus	36.85	359.74	876%	250.00	408.58	63%
Total Equity	411.85	734.74	78%	500.00	658.58	63%
Life Fund	7,684.56	9,782.51	27%	6,651.47	8,906.34	127%
First Premium	594.40	861.90	45%	502.60	844.20	68%
Gross Premium	2,320.70	3,201.20	38%	1,875.60	2,537.60	35%
Total Revenue	3,073.75	4,250.74	38%	2,415.39	3,314.00	37%
Net Premium	2,255.26	3,080.51	37%	1,538.55	1,868.87	21.47%
Investment Income	650.92	929.98	43%	312.42	491.91	57%
Management Expenses	287.06	389.86	36%	135.81	152.70	12%
Operating Expenses	123.19	104.11	-15%	41.59	39.47	-5%
Total Expenses	1,044.01	1,528.70	46%	619.40	904.46	46%
Net Profit	(66.38)	625.71		(25.13)	171.77	
Corporate tax to Government	4.96	43.95	786%	20.51	44.17	190%

Source: Annual Reports of Nepal Life and LIC

In FY 2012/13, Nepal Life has achieved 876%, 786%, 78% and 38% growth on reserves and Surplus, Corporate tax payment, equity capital and gross premium respectively. Similarly, LIC had

lead in other aspect. The growth rate of corporate tax payment, Life fund, First premium, investment income, total assets and investment assets is 190%, 127%, 68%, 57%, 35%, and 33% respectively. It is also shown that reserve and surplus fund of LIC is higher (Rs. 48.84 million) than Nepal Life and growth rate of management expenditure is lower than Nepal Life.

Two private life insurers have led the overall life insurance markets. Table 2 shows the total share of 8 life insurance companies and share of Nepal Life and LIC during FY 2012/13. Nepal Life covers 40% and LIC covers 36% of total assets whereas the portion of equity of Nepal Life and LIC is 21% and 12%. Private sector life insurance companies earned Rs. 9,439 million as net premium during FY 2012/13 which was contributed by Nepal Life and LIC almost one third and more than one fourth of total premium income earned by 8 LICs. In FY 2012/13, more than half net profit is shared by Nepal Life and 15% is shared by LIC. In 7 criteria viz. total assets, Equity, liabilities, net premium, investment assets and return and net profit, Nepal Life has led to LIC.

Rs. In million

Table 2: Market Share of Nepal Life and LIC in FY 2012/13

Parameter	Total of 8 LICs	Share of Nepal Life		Share of LIC	
		Amount	Share %	Amount	Share %
Total Assets	26,220	10,517	40%	9,315	36%
Equity	3,459	735	21%	409	12%
Liabilities	22,761	9,783	43%	8,906	39%
Net Premium	9,439	3,081	33%	2,526	27%
Investment Assets	26,101	11,227	43%	9,240	35%
Investment Return	2,618	956	37%	707	27%
Net Profit	1,135	626	55%	172	15%

Source: Annual Reports of Nepal Life and LIC

The objective of this paper is to analyse the profitability status of Nepal Life and LIC on the basis ratio analysis and compare the financial performance between two companies. Both LICs had started life insurance business from 2001 but analysis is done taking data for 6 years from 2007/08 to 2012/13.

Investment Income to Investment Assets Ratio

Investment assets means fund that has invested for the purpose of earning as per the Investment Directives of Insurance Board. The ratio reveals the efficiency of management and profitability position of firm. Life insurance companies need to construct their investment portfolio effectively so that return on investment can be maximised. Higher ratio means firm has been earning more income from its investment assets. Generally, the contribution of investment income to total income is on an average ranges from 15% to 20% which is considered as significant amount. Figure 1 shows investment income to investment assets ratio of two companies over previous six years. NL has earned more yield from their investment assets than LIC, however, yield of LIC during the six years period is not so fluctuate as the yield of NL. The industry average of investment yield during FY 2012/13 is 10.06%. Both companies yield is above the average.

Operating Expenses to Net Premiums Ratio

The ratio shows how efficiently firm is operating in minimum cost. Operating expense includes all non capital expenditure. Figure 2 shows that operational expenses ratio of both firm is increasing trend which is not good sign for the financial soundness of the company. The trend should be decreased as increase in the size of the business. Both companies' operating ratio reached maximum level for FY 2012/13 LIC's. The operating ratio of LIC is quite constant comparing to the ratio of Nepal life. Both companies need to pay attention to reduce the operating expenses. There is opposite relationship between profitability and expenses ratio.

Fig. 2: Operating Expenses/Gross Premium

Management Expenses to Net premiums Ratio

Management expenses means all non capital expenditure related to run day to day business. The example of expenses is: salary and allowance, business promotion, house rent etc. Regulator has paid serious attention to control the operating expense since the ratio should not be more than 30% for life insurance business. Higher ratio shows that the management is not efficient to operate the business. Both companies are running sufficiently lower than the prescribed management expenses ratio. Figure 2 indicates that the ratio of LIC's is less than that of Nepal Life. Obviously, management expenses ratio is gradually decreases over the period of time since the net premium earnings grows faster than management expenses. But,

Fig. 3: Management Expenses/Net Premium

Return on Assets

Return on Assets ratio indicates that capacity of assets to earn business profit. If the resources utilised effective manner, the ratio would be higher. The ratio is derived dividing the net profit by total Assets of the firm. The figure 4 makes clear that till 2011/12, the return was either negative or negligible but in FY 2012/13, ROE has increased to almost 6% of Nepal Life and 1.84% to LIC. Investments strategy of LIC is guided by directives of Insurance Board. Large portion (75%) of the LIC's investment assets need to invest in secure sector (Government Bond, FD of A and B class commercial banks. Figure 4 depicts that both companies have got momentum from FY 2012/13 where return on assets of Nepal Life is The industry average ROA for FY 2012/13 is 4.41%.

Fig. 4: Return on Assets

Return on Equity

Return on Equity ratio is widely used to measure the profitability of the firm. The ratio describes how effectively equity capital is utilised in business. Higher return on equity means higher rate of return on investment. Net profit to equity ratio over six years period of Nepal Life and LICs is shown in figure 5. The return on equity of both firm was negative last year but in FY 2012/13 it increased to 85% (Nepal Life) and 42% (LIC) which is good sign of financial performance. The reason behind the sudden raising of return on equity is base on valuation report of actuary. If life fund earn more return and management minimise the expenditure then return on equity also increases. So, there is close relationship among the investment income, premium income, operating ratio and return on equity. The industry average ROE for FY 2012/13 is 27.13%.

Fig. 5: Return on Equity

Net Profit Ratio

Profit is ultimate goal of any company and life insurance companies are not exception of this goal. Net profit ratio measures the firm profitability on the basis of its net premium and net profit. Figure 6 exposes the net profit margin of two firms for 6 years period. The ratio is calculated on the basis of before tax net profit to net premium. Comparing to previous years performance, both LICs have earned nice earning for FY 2012/13. Nepal Life's net profit is higher than LIC and industry average but LIC's

ratio is less than industry average. The industry average net profit margin for FY 2012/13 is 11.45%.

Fig. 6: Net Profit Margin

Base on the above discussion and analysis, a summary sheet has been prepared to find out which firm is performing well. On the basis of current year (FY 2012/13) performance a comparative sheet is prepared. Quantification is done assigning value 1 for better and value 0 for not better firm. Each criterion gets 1 mark. Table 4 shows the total marks obtained from each criterion. Nepal Life gets 4 marks and LIC gets 2 marks out of 6 criteria.

Table 4: Marking Financial Indicators of LICs by

Insurers/criteria	Net Profit Margin	Investment Income/Investment Assets	Return on Equity (ROE)	Return on Assets	Operating Expenses/Net Premium	Management Expenses/Net premiums	Total
NL	1	1	1	1			4
LIC					1	1	2

Government of Nepal had welcome foreign investment in insurance sector since 1967 and till date, 7 life and non life joint venture and foreign branches are doing insurance business. The financial performance of all domestic and joint venture from the single can say that foreign investment in insurance sector from long time.

CONCLUSION

Financial Performance of Life Insurance Companies can be measured using various tools. CAMELS parameter is popular to assess the financial performance. Due to the constraint of the size of the paper, we have used six different ratios to compare

the financial performance of Nepal Life and Life Insurance Corporation.

Among 6 criteria, expenses related criteria (Operating Expenses to Net Premium and Management Expenses to Net premiums) reveal that Life Insurance Corporation has done better performance than Nepal Life. The rest of four criteria related to return and earnings (Net Profit Margin, Investment Income to Investment Assets, Return on Equity and Return on Assets) show that Nepal Life has performed better than LIC. On the basis of six indicators financial performance of Nepal Life seems better during FY 2012/13.

Nepal Life had injected Rs. 125 million capital more than LIC, as a result, the amount of Assets, Equity, Life Fund, Net Premium, Investment Assets, Investment Return and Net Profit of Nepal Life is higher than LIC at the end of FY 2012/13 even though both companies had started business in the same year. Reserve and Surplus of LIC is higher (Rs. 48.84 million) than Nepal life and LIC had paid higher amount corporate tax (Rs. 0.22 million) in the same fiscal year.

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